

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF PRELOAD IN BOLTED COMPOSITE JOINTS WITH TEMPERATURE LOADS

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Keywords: Pretensioned bolted joints, Orthotropic linear viscoelasticity

ABSTRACT

Pretensioned bolted joints of polymer matrix composite structural components show a loss of preload due to viscoelastic properties of the matrix and a load direction perpendicular to fiber orientation. In this work, an experimental investigation and a numerical prediction of the bolt preload is performed for three different T700 Epoxy laminate plates at room temperature and at 70 °C. Bolt preload is measured by using an embedded strain gauge inside M 8 bolts as well as by force washers for a period of up to 48 days without external loadings. The simulation is carried out in two ways: viscoelastic exact solution and quasi-elastic approach using a three-dimensional finite element model of test setup, differences between both methods are negligible. The numerical analysis show a high influence of fiber volume fraction and laminate thickness on preload behaviour. Compared to the test results, simulation gives lower preload losses. Furthermore, the test results show a lower influence of laminate layup on bolt preload behaviour at room temperature than at 70 °C. The comparison of test results between quasi-isotropic laminate and steel specimen show an almost identical preload loss at room temperature, whereas the preload loss of quasi-isotropic laminate is approximately twice of steel specimen at 70°C.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today, composite materials are used in a wide field of structural applications. Besides the common joining techniques for composites, “bonding”, “riveting”, and “bearing”, pretensioned bolted joints can be very useful depending on the application and the requirements. Pretensioned bolted joints are especially useful when tolerance compensation as well as detachability are main requirements. The force transmission between the clamped parts is accomplished by friction, the magnitude of the friction forces is determined by the preload from tightening the bolt. Thus, a certain magnitude of preload is necessary to transmit the external loads in order to maintain the correct functionality of the load introduction in operation. Detailed knowledge of preload during mounting and operation allows a light and cost-effective design of the load introduction area.

In contrast to metallic pretensioned joints, where design methods are well known and understood; there are challenges for efficiently designing composite bolted joints because of the anisotropic and non-homogeneous nature of composite materials. The bolt preload acts perpendicular to laminate plane. Thus, the preload is mostly transmitted by the weak polymer matrix. Since polymers show viscoelastic properties depending on temperature [5], bolt preload decreases with time and can fall below the critical design limit. Essentially, there are three main effects influencing bolt preload relaxation [7]: seating, which occurs directly after tightening, (local) load plastifications, and creeping, which affects long time preload behaviour. The magnitude of these effects depends on material, temperature/moisture, surface conditions of the clamped parts, and mechanical loads. Compared to metallic structures, the use of composites causes additional parameters influencing preload relaxation, viz. fiber/matrix properties, fiber volume fraction φ_F , and composite layup. Since fibers are elastic, they are able to restrict matrix creeping in fiber direction. Thus, laminate layup should have an influence on bolt preload.

Preload behaviour over time of pretensioned bolted composite joints has already been investigated for a long time. Shivakumar and Crews [15] predict the preload loss in a linear viscoelastic finite element analysis (FEA) for a quasi-isotropic graphite epoxy laminate ($\varphi_F = 0.63$) in a double-lap joint to 30 %

after 20 years at room temperature (RT). Analysis show a higher preload loss for increased temperature and moisture content. In [16] tests are carried out on unidirectional carbon laminates using hexagonal head bolts in a three point bending test under static and dynamic loading. Experimental results show a bolt relaxation of 1.25 - 4.25 % after 30 h at RT and are compared to a quasi-elastic FEA. The studies of Caccese et al. in [6] reveal a preload loss of 55 % after 2000 h for a bolted joint with a hybrid composite - metal configuration. In [7] tests were conducted with T300 Epoxy ($0^\circ/90^\circ$ bidirectional, $\varphi_F = 0.6$) and T300 PEEK laminates (atlas weave, $\varphi_F = 0.5$) at 80°C and 100°C using countersunk screws and a micrometer spindle for preload measurement. The Epoxy specimen show a remaining preload of approximately 35 % and the PEEK specimen more than 60 % after 500 h at 80°C . Furthermore, a dependency of initial preload could be demonstrated where an increased preload level leads to a decreased preload loss.

In framework of this paper, the preload behaviour of pretensioned bolted composite joints is determined by experimental investigations and numerical simulations considering temperature effects and neglecting moisture influences. Important influences on bolt preload, such as layup, fiber volume fraction, and laminate thickness, are studied. Moreover, the orthotropic viscoelastic exact solution is compared to the quasi-elastic approach in the simulations.

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

Bolt preload is determined by measuring the tensile strain of the bolt using an embedded strain gauge. The preloaded bolt clamps a single laminate without external loading. The time dependent preload behaviour is investigated at room temperature and 70°C .

2.1 Test - Setup and Specimens

Bolt preload tests are performed using standard ISO metric M 8 hexagonal head bolts (8.8 DIN 933). The bolt preload is determined by measuring the tensile strain of the bolt, Figure 1. A special bolt strain gauge (Typ BTM-1C from manufacturer "Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo Co., Ltd., [17]") is bonded into a small pre-drilled hole with a diameter of 1.6 mm by a two-component epoxy adhesive. The axial position of the strain gauge and the depth of the hole has to be within the shank region of the bolt to avoid influences of the thread. Tests are performed on single laminate plates without any external or operating loads respectively. Overall dimensions of the specimens are 200 mm x 80 mm minimum. Through holes have a diameter of 8.3 mm and are located at half width of the specimen to provide a sufficient distance to the edges of the laminate plates. Carbon epoxy laminates with three different layups (quasi-isotropic, $0^\circ/90^\circ$ biaxial, unidirectional) and a common steel sheet are investigated, too. Details of specimens can be found in Table 1. Due to the small thickness of the plates and length of bolt shank, two steel washers with a thickness of 8 mm are used to ensure that the specimen can be clamped and the strain gauge is located in the region of the specimen.

Figure 1: Test setup with an embedded stain gauge (left) and test setup with an additional force washer (right)

In addition to the strain gauges, two force washers for M 8 bolts from different manufactures (HBM, Inc. [8] and ME-Messsysteme GmbH [12]) are used in two test setups. Due to the built-in strain gauge in form of a full bridge, these sensors are resistant to temperature variations and thus well suited for long

running measurements. The maximum operating conditions are given to 40 kN pressure force and a maximum operating temperature of 70 °C. With regard to the test setup, one of the thick washers is replaced by a force washer and two additional thinner washers (Figure 1 right).

Specimen	Layup	Fiber volume fraction [-]	Thickness [mm]
T700 Epoxy (QI)	[0/90/+45/-45] _s (*)	0.48	2.9
T700 Epoxy (0°/90°)	0°/90° biaxial fabric	0.50	2.2
T700 Epoxy (UD)	[0] ₆	0.58	2.2
Steel sheet	-	-	2.2

Table 1: Specimens for bolt preload tests (*with additional glass fabric on outer surfaces: 2 x 0.1 mm)

For each layup two specimens with two or three bolts are prepared, one specimen for the test at RT and one at a temperature of 70 °C. Thermal load is applied by a temperature chamber. Strain gauges and force washers are connected to a multiple measuring amplifier (Type UPM 100 Hottinger Baldwin Messtechnik). Prior to the tests, a temperature compensation for the test setup with the embedded strain gauges is conducted to minimize temperature errors. Each unloaded bolt is slowly heated up from RT to 70 °C. Resulting strain versus temperature is recorded and fitted by a polynomial function. This data will be considered in the evaluation of the tests. Bolts are tightened with 25 Nm using a torque wrench and put in the temperature chamber where they are heated up at a rate of approximately 50 °C/h. When 70 °C are reached, temperature is held constant over the whole period of testing. Room temperature as well as chamber temperature are additionally measured by thermocouples. All acquired data is logged at a data rate of 1 sample per two minutes. Test duration is approximately 48 days maximum. The experimental setup is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Test setup under room temperature conditions (left) and in temperature chamber (right)

2.2 Experimental Results

For better comparability of the test results, the measured tensile strain of the bolts $\varepsilon_M(t)$ is normalized to the maximum strain after torquing (assembly state), indicated by an over-bar. This normalized strain $\bar{\varepsilon}_M(t)$ is equivalent to the normalized bolt preload. Figure 3 shows the test data of the T700 Epoxy quasi-isotropic laminate at RT and 70 °C. Results of the tests with the force washers (f.w.) are listed as well. Bolts “RT 03” and “RT f.w.” were loosened after approximately 20 days, the other bolts after approximately 48 days. The bolts used for the tests at 70 °C were loosened after cooling them down to RT.

Figure 4 shows certain details in the beginning of the 70 °C test and in the end of the test. A sharp drop of preload can be noticed in the beginning before the specimens are heated up. Thus, the bolt preload increases caused by thermal expansion of the laminate due to a greater coefficient of thermal expansion in thickness direction of the laminates compared to steel (bolt and washers). At the same time, the creep behaviour of matrix material of the laminate changes resulting in a larger decrease rate of the bolt preload compared to RT. In a similar way, the preload decreases when cooling down.

After loosening at $t = t_L$ a non-negligible remaining negative strain $\bar{\varepsilon}_M(t_L)$ is measured in the unloaded bolts. This apparent strain can be observed for all bolts with embedded strain gauges after

loosening. However, the magnitude of this remaining apparent strain is different from specimen to specimen. It is most important for the specimens exposed to elevated temperatures. Obviously, additional effects or mechanisms during the tests occurred, perhaps caused by micro cracks, imperfections or dirt particles in the adhesive or creeping of the adhesive itself. Thus, the strain gauge relaxed with time. After loosening, it is compressed by the bolt contraction resulting in a negative apparent strain.

Figure 3: Measured bolt preload for T700 Epoxy quasi-isotropic laminate

Considering the force washers, a remaining strain after loosening the bolts can also be observed, however, the magnitude of this apparent strain is small and well within the accuracy of these load cells given by the manufacturer.

Figure 4: Starting and ending time of T700 Epoxy quasi-isotropic laminate at 70 °C

The measured data has to be corrected for the apparent strain $\bar{\epsilon}_M(t_L)$. At time t_L the real strain in the bolt has to be zero, thus adding $-\bar{\epsilon}_M(t_L)$ to the measured strain yields the correct value. However, this is valid for the loosening point in time t_L only. In order to get the real normalized strain of the bolt $\bar{\epsilon}(t)$ for the whole testing period, an assumption for the time behaviour of the apparent strain $\bar{\epsilon}_R(t)$ with the conditions $\bar{\epsilon}_R(0) = 0$ and $\bar{\epsilon}_R(t_L) = \bar{\epsilon}_M(t_L)$ is made:

$$|\bar{\epsilon}_R(t)| = at^n. \quad (1)$$

This function has the form of a power law with two parameters a and n . It has a similar shape as the measured data. The exponent n is assumed to be small ($= 0.2$), because the discussed processes in the

adhesive happen faster in the beginning of the test than in the end, similar to a creep function. Furthermore, a small value of the exponent effects the important time domain in the end of measurement in a minor way so that the resulting error is quite low. Using the assumed exponent n , the parameter a is determined from following equation:

$$a = \left| \frac{\bar{\varepsilon}_R(t_L)}{t_L^n} \right|. \quad (2)$$

Finally, the normalized bolt strain $\bar{\varepsilon}(t)$ and normalized bolt preload $\bar{F}(t)$ respectively can be written as:

$$\bar{F}(t) = \bar{\varepsilon}(t) = \bar{\varepsilon}_M(t) + |\bar{\varepsilon}_R(t)|. \quad (3)$$

This procedure is carried out for all data curves and specimens, results are shown in Figure 6. For most data curves in a period $12 \leq t \leq 16$ days and $31.5 \leq t \leq 34$ days there is a lack of data due to a shutdown of the logging computer. Furthermore, some data curves show a small change in bolt preload in the region of $t = 6$ days caused by a failure of the laboratory air conditioning system.

In contrast to steel, test results for laminate specimens show a relative high temperature dependency. Moreover, it can be seen that at RT the normalized bolt preload for the specimens with quasi-isotropic laminate is greater than that for biaxial and unidirectional laminate. The highest bolt preload loss occurs for the specimens with unidirectional laminate at 70°C.

Figure 5: Test results for QI after evaluation according to Eq. (3)

Figure 6: Test results for UD, 0°/90°, and steel (from left to right) after evaluation according to Eq. (3)

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

A 3D-finite element analysis is performed to predict the bolt preload behaviour using ANSYS v.16.0. The viscoelastic relaxation matrix for a unidirectional ply is determined by a representative volume element (RVE). Viscoelastic exact solution [9] and the quasi-elastic approach [9, 11] are investigated.

3.1 Numerical Homogenization

A 3D-finite element model of a RVE [3] is used to calculate the relaxation matrix of a unidirectional ply, Figure 7. It consists of a hexagonal arrangement of fibers assuming that the structure is periodically with one round fiber in the center and a fourth of a fiber at each of the four edges. Periodical boundary conditions are applied on all surfaces. The structure is fixed supported at one node in the center of the RVE.

Figure 7: Finite element mesh of RVE with fibers (cyan) and matrix (red) [3]

The polymer matrix material is assumed to be linear viscoelastic isotropic; the carbon fibers are orthotropic elastic. Due to a lack of creep and relaxation data for the epoxy used in the specimens, creep functions from Beckwith [4] for a Shell 58-68R Epoxy resin are used instead. Beckwith performed in his work several short time creep tests for approximately 100 min at different temperatures from RT 75 °F (= 23.89 °C) up to 160 °F (= 71.1 °C) and fitted the data by a power law:

$$D(t) = D_o + D_1 t^n, \quad (4)$$

where $D(t)$ [MPa⁻¹] indicates the creep function (or creep compliance), D_o [MPa⁻¹] the initial creep value, D_1 [MPa⁻¹ min⁻ⁿ] the creep coefficient, and n a dimensionless creep exponent. Since the testing period of up to 48 days is much longer than the available creep test data, an extrapolation has to be made. Therefore, the time temperature superposition principle can be used [2, 13]. This implies that viscoelastic behaviour at higher temperatures is analog to that at lower temperatures but at another time scale. In other words, influences of temperature T and time t on the creep behaviour can be described by one parameter, the reduced time $\xi = t/a_T$. In this, a_T indicates the shifting factor, which depends on the resin and the temperature and has to be calculated for each creep test at a temperature higher than RT (= reference temperature). The shifting factor is defined by the amount on a logarithmic time plot by which a creep function at a higher temperature has to be horizontal shifted until it optimally fits the creep function at reference temperature (here: 23.8 °C). Therefore, a short time creep test at a reference temperature can be extrapolated by shifting creep functions for the same test at higher temperatures (construction of a master curve). Ageing effects are not considered.

Since all creep functions from Beckwith's creep tests have the same exponent n , the power law at RT with the same constants can be used for the extrapolation at RT. Maximum extrapolation time is limited by the creep test at the highest temperature (71.1 °C). Shifting factor for this temperature is $a_T = 0.00278$ resulting in the maximum extrapolation time of 100 min/0.00278 \approx 25 days. It is assumed that the power law at 71.1 °C can be extrapolated in the same way as at RT (no creep data for higher temperatures are given). Constants for power law are listed in Table 2.

T [°C]	D_o [10 ⁻⁴ MPa ⁻¹]	D_1 [10 ⁻⁵ MPa ⁻¹ min ⁻ⁿ]	n [-]
23.8	2.7310	1.0008	0.19
71.1	3.0023	3.6349	0.19

Table 2: Constants of power law for Epoxy resin Shell 58-68R [4]

The creep function from Eq. (4) has to be transformed into the relaxation function of the matrix $C(t)$ to get the input data for ANSYS. This can be done in two ways: viscoelastic exact solution and quasi-elastic approach. It is expected that both methods are in good coincidence [11]. With regard to the correspondence principle the viscoelastic exact solution is defined as [3]:

$$C(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{D(s)s^2} \right\}, \quad (5)$$

where $D(s)$ is the Laplace transformation of $D(t)$ and \mathcal{L}^{-1} indicates the inverse Laplace transformation. The quasi-elastic approach can be written as [11]:

$$C(t) = \frac{1}{D(t)}. \quad (6)$$

Results for both methods show a high coincidence, Figure 8.

Figure 8: Matrix relaxation function $C(t)$ determined by viscoelastic exact solution and quasi-elastic approach

ANSYS requires the input of time dependent bulk and shear modulus in form of Prony-series [1]. Under the assumption that the Poisson's ratio of matrix material is constant in time, Prony-series parameters for bulk and shear modulus are identical. Therefore, the relaxation function is fitted with the Prony-series:

$$C(t) = C_0 \left[1 - \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}} \right) \right], \quad (7)$$

with elastic modulus C_0 , relative relaxation moduli $\alpha_i = C_i/C_0$ and relaxation times τ_i . Fitting is carried out in MATLAB R2014a using the nonlinear curve fitting algorithm *lsqcurvefit* [10]. A high level of accuracy is achieved by using 7 or 8 terms. Values for α_i and τ_i can be found in Table 3. Fiber properties except ν_{f23} are listed in Table 4 and taken from literature [14] for HT fiber.

i	α_i (23.8°C)	τ_i (23.8°C)	α_i (71.1°C)	τ_i (71.1°C)
1	0.0194	2.1658E+01	0.0758	8.1115E-01
2	0.0371	3.4658E+03	0.0540	1.0167E+03
3	0.0285	6.6577E+02	0.0385	1.3125E+01
4	0.0219	1.2840E+02	0.0409	6.0926E+01
5	0.0299	9.4176E-01	0.0438	9.0574E-04
6	0.0147	9.2257E-04	0.0655	4.2393E+03
7	0.0849	2.7578E+04	0.0469	2.4946E+02
8			0.1284	2.8726E+04

Table 3: Prony-series parameters for viscoelastic Epoxy matrix material

E_{f1} [MPa]	E_{f2} [MPa]	G_{f12} [MPa]	ν_{f12} [-]	ν_{f23} [-]
230 000	28 000	50 000	0.23	0.4*

Table 4: HT-fiber properties [13] (*assumption)

The 3D-transversally isotropic time dependent relaxation matrix $[C]$ of the RVE is determined from equation according to [3]:

$$\underbrace{\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_1 \\ \bar{\sigma}_2 \\ \bar{\sigma}_3 \\ \bar{\tau}_{23} \\ \bar{\tau}_{31} \\ \bar{\tau}_{21} \end{Bmatrix}}_{\{\bar{\sigma}\}(t)} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{23} & C_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix}}_{[C](t)} \underbrace{\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_3 \\ \gamma_{23} \\ \gamma_{31} \\ \gamma_{21} \end{Bmatrix}}_{\{\varepsilon\}} \quad \text{with } C_{44} = \frac{1}{2}(C_{22} - C_{23}), \quad (8)$$

where “1” denotes the fiber direction. Constant strains $\{\varepsilon\}$ are applied of the RVE and the resulting averaged stresses $\{\bar{\sigma}\}$ are determined for each point in time. These stresses are used for the calculation of the components of $[C]$. Figure 9 shows the relaxation matrix components C_{ij} for an unidirectional ply of the T700 Epoxy quasi-isotropic specimen with laminate properties from Table 1, matrix properties from Table 2, and fiber properties from Table 4. Subsequently, the components $C_{ij}(t)$ are fitted with a Prony-series according to Eq. (7). Changes of the stiffness component $C_{11}(t)$ over time are negligible (0.6 % at RT and 1.3 % at 70°C), simulations are carried out with constant C_{11} .

 Figure 9: Relaxation matrix components $C_{ij}(t)$ for T700 Epoxy unidirectional ply with $\varphi_F = 0.48$

3.2 Pretensioned Bolted Composite Joint Modelling

A 3D-finite element model of the test setup is created to predict the bolt preload behaviour clamping different laminates. The model includes bolt as cylindrical part without thread, washers, and laminate (see Figure 10), however, only one fourth of complete test setup is modeled for reasons of symmetry. On the two cutting planes, symmetrical boundary conditions are applied. The model consists of 29474 elements. Contacts between laminate and washers as well as between bolt and washers are considered. Coefficients of static frictions are assumed to 0.2 and 0.1. Preload is applied in form of constant

displacement using pretension elements in the bolt. This displacement is held constant during the simulation, thus bolt preload can change with time. The preload is calculated from the tensile stress of the bolt in the pretension section and the shank cross sectional area of the bolt.

Figure 10: Finite element model including bolt, washers and specimen showing stress distribution in thickness direction (units: MPa)

Each unidirectional laminate ply is modeled as a layer with one element in thickness direction. Viscoelastic material properties of 3D-unidirectional lamina are taken from the RVE results, Figure 9. Solutions are done for the quasi-elastic approach and the viscoelastic exact method. The first one is realized by performing single elastic calculations using material properties at a certain point in time. The second one needs more modelling afford of the material because there is no orthotropic viscoelastic material model available in ANSYS. Therefore, an existing material model from Hinterhoelzl's work [9] in form of an ABAQUS subroutine is used and converted to an ANSYS compatible subroutine. This subroutine is then linked with ANSYS through the usermat interface building a dynamic link library. Within this subroutine the constitutive equation (in tensor notation):

$$\sigma_{ij} = \int_{-0}^{\xi} C_{ijkl}(\xi - \xi') \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{kl}(\xi')}{\partial \xi'} \partial \xi' \quad \text{with} \quad \xi(t) = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a_T(T(t))} , \quad (9)$$

which is also known as Boltzmann's superposition principle, is implemented. Therein $\xi(t)$ indicates the reduced time from time temperature superposition principle and C_{ijkl} the relaxation function in form of a Prony-series according to Eq. (7). This procedure is applicable for linear viscoelastic materials without aging effects and isothermal conditions.

3.3 Numerical Results

The laminates (listed in Table 4) have different fiber volume fractions, laminate thicknesses t_{lam} , and layups. In order to determine the influence of layup on the bolt preload, the thickness and the fiber volume fraction is assumed to $t_{lam} = 2.2$ mm and $\varphi_F = 0.5$ for all laminates. The simulation results show the same bolt preload after 20 days for the quasi-isotropic and the bidirectional laminate, Table 5. This results from the identical changes of laminate stiffness in thickness direction with time for both laminates. The bolt preload for the unidirectional laminate is only slightly lower compared to the other laminates (0.2 % at RT and 0.5 % at 70°C). A thicker laminate and thus a greater grip length leads to a decreased bolt preload: e.g. 93.3 % at RT and 80.8 % at 70 °C for the quasi-isotropic laminate with assumed properties $t_{lam} = 2.2$ mm and $\varphi_F = 0.5$.

	QI	0°/90°	UD
RT	94.06 %	94.06 %	93.84 %
70 °C	82.94 %	82.95 %	82.43 %

Table 5: Normalized bolt preload from viscoelastic FEA using identical laminate thickness and fiber volume fraction after 20 days

Results from numerical analysis for the orthotropic viscoelastic exact case and the quasi-elastic approach are given in Figure 11 using laminate properties from Table 4. Both solutions for the normalized bolt preload start at “1” in the beginning at $t = 0$ indicating the elastic case. With increasing time, there are only negligible differences between both approaches (0.15 % after 20 days), at which the quasi-elastic approach leads to slightly higher preloads compared to the exact solution. Furthermore, it can be seen that at RT and also at 70 °C the normalized bolt preload is highest for the unidirectional laminate followed by 0°/90° laminate. This result is due to different fiber volume fractions and laminate thicknesses.

Figure 11: Comparison between the viscoelastic exact solution (ve) and the quasi-elastic approach (qe) for different T700 Epoxy laminates (fvf = fiber volume fraction, $t = t_{lam}$)

4 COMPARISON BETWEEN EXPERIMENT AND FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Numerical results from the viscoelastic simulation and the averaged test results are summarized in Figure 12 after a testing period of 20 days. There are some differences between numerical and test results which need to be discussed:

1. Numerical results should be lower than test results because in the simulation only influences of matrix relaxation on bolt preload are taken into account. In contrast, during the tests other effects besides matrix creeping have an impact on bolt preload, e.g. seating between bolt head or nut and specimen as well as local load plastifications resulting in an increased bolt preload loss. Test results of the UD and 0°/90° laminate confirm this statement.
2. The matrix creep data was taken from literature and does not match exactly the epoxy data of the specimens. In addition, the applicability of time temperature superposition principle for extrapolation is an assumption that needs to be verified by a long time creep test – especially at a temperature of 70 °C.
3. The creep behaviour is assumed to be linear viscoelastic in the simulation, but for increased stress levels it shows a nonlinear behaviour [4, 14].

Test results show that the layout of the laminates has greater influence on the preload behaviour at higher temperature than at lower temperatures. Additionally, fiber volume fraction and laminate thickness seem to play a minor role in test results, whereas the layout is an important parameter. Another

essential point is that for the quasi-isotropic laminate and the steel specimen a nearly similar preload loss at RT (8.8 % and 7.6 %) occurs. At a temperature of 70 °C, the quasi-isotropic laminate shows a considerably greater preload loss than the steel specimens, resulting from greater temperature dependency of the epoxy material.

Figure 12: Preload loss from viscoelastic FEA and averaged test results from Figure 5 and Figure 6 after 20 days

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, experimental and numerical investigations were carried out to determine the preload loss of pretensioned bolted composite joints at RT and at 70 °C. Bolt preload was measured using strain gauges embedded in M 8 bolts. Tests were conducted for different T700 epoxy laminates (quasi-isotropic, 0°/90° biaxial fabric and unidirectional with different fiber volume fractions and thicknesses) over a period of 48 days maximum. Results from the tests show a low influence of layup on preload at RT (preload loss is 14 % after 20 days), whereas at 70 °C greater differences between laminates can be observed. The comparison between steel and quasi-isotropic laminate shows almost the same preload behaviour at RT.

Finite element analysis for this application shows that the quasi-elastic approach is a very good method to describe orthotropic viscoelastic material behaviour in pretensioned bolted joints. This is particularly important because an orthotropic viscoelastic material model is not yet implemented in the most commercial finite element tools. Numerical results show a greater influence of fiber volume fraction and laminate thickness on the preload loss than test results. Layup of the laminates is more important at higher temperature than at lower temperatures concluding from tests. Almost the same preload loss occurs for the quasi-isotropic and the steel specimen at RT. The comparison between tests and simulations show some differences which should be considered in future.

Therefore, more tests need to be conducted using laminates with different fiber volume fractions and thicknesses. At the moment, tests are carried out using carbon and glass thermoplastic composites. Furthermore, a characterization of creep behaviour of the used epoxy material has to be done to enable an update of the material model for simulation. It is also necessary to perform tests with a pure epoxy specimen and calculate an averaged creep function from preload measurements which can be used in simulations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) supporting the scientific researches in the framework of the project MAI Last (grant: 03MAI13A), which is a part of leading-edge cluster MAI Carbon.

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